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SPATIAL DISTRIBUTION OF DIFFERENT TYPES OF DEGRADED AND WASTELANDS IN INDIA: A CASE STUDY OF BIHAR

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ABSTRACT

India is land of farmers. More than 70 per cent of India's population is living in rural areas with agriculture as their livelihood support system. Sustainable agricultural development and food security will be one of the key challenges for India in this century because the task of providing food security to our country's burgeoning population is becoming increasingly difficult. This challenge must and needs to be met in the face of the changing consumption pattern, impacts of climate change and the degradation of the finite land and water resources. The vast majority of Indian farmers are small and marginal. Their farm size is decreasing further and per capita availability of inelastic land resource is rapidly declining in relation to annual population growth of 1.58 per cent in the country. The quality of land is deteriorating due to heightened nutrient mining, soil erosion, increasing water scarcity, adverse impact of climate change and accumulation of toxic elements in soil and water. Increasing GDP growth is expanding urbanization and industrialization and, therefore, more and more agricultural lands are being utilized for non-agricultural purposes. The complex interplay of natural and anthropogenic processes compounds problems of land use planning further. All of these factors combined with increased rate of land degradation are contributing towards decline in agricultural productivity leading to food insecurity. State level and country level information has already been published by the National Remote Sensing Agency (now NRSC). The first order need of the day, therefore, is to prepare a national degraded and wastelands map downscaled to districts. In the present paper an attempt has been made to discuss the nature and causes of the land degradation, its spatial distribution and the determination of degree and extent of damaged lands in general at national level and in particular at the state level i.e. Bihar. So that developmental agencies in participation with stakeholders proactively adopt measures to reclaim degraded lands for distancing food insecurity, a real challenge.

Keywords: *Spatial Distribution, Degraded land, Wasteland*

INTRODUCTION

India shares 17 per cent of the world population, while its land is 2 per cent of the total geographical area of the world. Naturally, the pressure on the land is beyond its carrying capacity. Therefore, the productive lands,

especially the farmlands in India are in the constant process of various degrees of degradation and are fast turning into wastelands. At present, approximately 68.35 million hectare area of land is lying as wastelands in India. Out of these lands,

approximately 50 per cent lands are such non-forest lands, which can be made fertile again if treated properly. It was unprotected non-forest lands, which suffered the maximum degradation mainly due to the tremendous biotic pressure on it. In the last 50 years it is India's lush green village forests and woodlots have been deforested to the maximum, To restore this ecological imbalance, the Government of India had created the Department of Wasteland Development to develop the degraded non-forest wastelands. The wastelands represent underutilization of resources. In fact, the prevalence of poverty, malnutrition, hunger and regional inequality is to some extent due to underutilization of resources particularly in India, it exists in the form of wastelands. It could be noted that a country like Japan has inadequate land area with high density of population, but it has achieved a high rate of economic development, indicating their intensive effort towards better utilization of resources. In India, despite having a large land area, the problem of underutilization of resources persists in different parts of the country. Hence, there is a growing concern on wasteland development in India.

Since land resources are finite, requisite measures are required to reclaim degraded and wastelands. So that areas going out of cultivation due to social and economic reasons are replenished by reclaiming these lands and by arresting further loss of production potential.

In this direction, an effective utilization, rejuvenation and management of degraded and wastelands by public and private investment become imperative. As a first step, a reliable set of estimates of the

degraded and wastelands is essential. In addition to the type and the extent of degradation the lands have undergone or are undergoing, appropriate management strategies need to be designed.

METHODOLOGY

The present study is mainly based on secondary data because the area of study is very vast. The data pertaining to the present study was collected from the published documents of Ministry of Agriculture, different journals, magazines and also from the Internet.

The compiled data on different subjects have been tabulated. Synthesis, perusal and analysis of data have been carried out with the help of simple statistical techniques. In the table the rank and percentile analysis has been produced that contains the ordinal and percentage rank of each state in data set. It is for analyzing the relative standing of land degradation in India and Bihar as well.

CATEGORIES OF WASTE LANDS IN INDIA

In India there are two types of wastelands in general i.e. *ecological wastelands* and *developmental wastelands*. The ecological wastelands consist of degraded forests, gullied and ravenous lands, marked hill slopes, saline-alkali soils, deserts, sand dunes and shifting cultivation areas. The developmental wastelands include mine spoils areas, water logged areas formed by seepage of canal irrigation, foreshores of irrigation reservoirs, industrial wastelands, land strip cleared for laying of electric transmission and so on. Area wise detailed account of categories of wastelands is given below respectively, (Table 1).

Table-1 Categories of Wastelands in India

S.No.	Category	Area (in sq.Kms.)
1	Snow covered/Glacial	55788.49
2	Barren rocky/Sheet Rock	64584.77
3	Sands-inland/Coastal	50021.65
4	Land affected by Salinity/ alkalinity	20477.38
5	Gullied/or ravenous land	20553.35
6	Upland with or without scrub	194014.29
7	Water logged & marshy	16568.45
8	Steep sloping area	7656.29
9	Shifting cultivation land	35142.2
10	Mining/industrial wastelands	1252.13
11	Degraded/pastures/grazing land	25978.91
12	Underutilized/degraded notified forest land	140652.31
13	Degraded land under plantation crop	5828.09

Grand Total: 638518. 31 Sq.Kms.

In this context, it is important to highlight the extent of variation in the spatial distribution of wastelands throughout the country. In fact, in India the wasteland ranges from 38 to 187

million hectares, according to the estimates given by different agencies with diverse classification strategies, table 2.

Table-2 Estimate of Wastelands from Different Sources

S. No.	Sources	Area (m.ha)	Estimated (E) / Scientific
1	National Commission on Agriculture(NCA-1976)	175.00	E
2	Directorate of Economics and Statistics, Department of Agriculture and Cooperation	38.40	E
3	Ministry of Agriculture (1982)	175.00	E
4	Department of Environment and Forest	95.00	E
5	National Wasteland Development Board	123.00	E
6	NBBS and LUP, ICAR, 1994	187.00	E
7	Society for Promotion of Wastelands	129.00	E
8	# National Remote Sensing Agency, 1995	75.50	S
9	Dr.N.C. Saxena (Secretary RD-WD)	125.00	E

The figure of 75.50 m.ha is derived from the results of land use/land cover mapping done on 1:250,000 scale during 1989-90, using satellite data at the request of Planning Commission for increasing food production in various Agro-climatic zones.

SPATIAL DISTRIBUTION OF DEGRADED AND WASTELANDS IN INDIA

So far as the spatial distribution of degraded and wastelands in India is concerned, no doubt, it gives a highly erratic

picture. Some of the states have very high percentage of wasteland, while some states have very low percentage of wasteland and in some of the states the land degradation is even less than one per cent. State wise area statistics of degraded and wastelands is shown in table 3, map-1. In the given table the rank and percentile analysis has been produced that contains the ordinal and percentage rank of each state in data set. It is for analyzing the relative standing of land degradation in India.

Table – 3 State Wise Total Geographical Area And Degraded Land In India - 2011

S.No.	STATE	TGA	LD	% LD OF TGA
1	Andhrapradesh	275045.0	9193.0	3.34
2	Andaman & Nicobar	8249.0	71.0	0.86
3	Arunachalpradesh	83743.0	2154.0	2.57
4	Assam	78438.0	4571.0	5.83
5	Bihar	94163.0	1371.0	1.46
6	Chhattisgarh	134805.0	4784.0	3.55
7	Delhi	1483.0	28.0	1.89
8	Goa	3702.0	122.0	3.30
9	Gujarat	196042.0	3129.0	1.60
10	Haryana	44212.0	551.0	1.25
11	Himachalpradesh	55673.0	1065.0	1.91
12	Jammu & Kashmir	222236.0	2094.0	0.94
13	Jharkhand	79714.0	3943.0	4.95
14	Karnataka	191791.0	8093.0	4.22
15	Kerala	38863.0	2608.0	6.71
16	Madhyapradesh	308641.0	14095.0	4.57
17	Maharashtra	307713.0	9728.0	3.16
18	Manipur	22327.0	1768.0	7.92
19	Meghalaya	22429.0	1732.0	7.72
20	Mizoram	21081.0	1163.0	5.52
21	Nagaland	16579.0	1550.0	9.35
22	Orissa	155707.0	3722.0	2.39
23	Punjab	50362.0	494.0	0.98
24	Rajasthan	342239.0	20424.0	5.97

25	Sikkim	7096.0	60.0	0.85
26	Tamil Nadu	130058.0	2997.0	2.30
27	Tripura	10486.0	785.0	7.49
28	Uttarpradesh	238566.0	14405.0	6.04
29	Uttarakhand	55845.0	1435.0	2.57
30	West Bengal	88752.0	2140.0	2.41
Total		3286040.0	120275.0	113.59

TGA – Total Geographical Area (Hectare), LD – Land degraded (Hectare)

Map - 1

On the basis of the above table, the following table-4 has been prepared in which land degradation percent of total geographical area, rank and their percentile at the state level in India has been calculated according to the available statistics of 2011.

DATA ANALYSIS

So far as the state wise wasteland area statistics of India is concerned, out of thirty states, land degradation per cent out of their total geographical area has been divided into

five categories, i.e. very high, high, medium, low, and very low respectively.

In the first order category of states, the land degradation is very high (7.49-9.35%). In this category only four states are included i.e. Nagaland, Manipur, Meghalaya and Tripura. These states are in descending order of their land degradation among which Nagaland has the highest land degradation (9.35%) and Tripura has the lowest percent of land degradation (7.49%).

TABLE – 4 - LAND DDEGRADION PERCENT OF TOTAL GEOGRAPHICAL AREA, RANK AND PERCENTILE IN INDIA - 2011			
S.NO. OF TABLE- 3	LD % OF TGA	RANK	PERCENTILE
21	9.35	1	100.00%
18	7.92	2	96.50%
19	7.72	3	93.10%
27	7.49	4	89.60%
15	6.71	5	86.20%
28	6.04	6	82.70%
24	5.97	7	79.30%
4	5.83	8	75.80%
20	5.52	9	72.40%
13	4.95	10	68.90%
16	4.57	11	65.50%
14	4.22	12	62.00%
6	3.55	13	58.60%
1	3.34	14	55.10%
8	3.30	15	51.70%
17	3.16	16	48.20%
3	2.57	17	44.80%
29	2.57	18	41.30%
30	2.41	19	37.90%
22	2.39	20	34.40%
26	2.30	21	31.00%
11	1.91	22	27.50%
7	1.89	23	24.10%
9	1.60	24	20.60%
5	1.46	25	17.20%
10	1.25	26	13.70%
23	0.98	27	10.30%
12	0.94	28	6.80%
2	0.86	29	3.40%
25	0.85	30	0.00%

TGA – Total Geographical Area (Hectare), LD – Land degraded (Hectare)

In the second order category of states where the land degradation is high (4.95-6.71%), only six states are included, i.e. Kerala, Uttarpradesh, Rajasthan, Assam, Mezoram, and Jharkhand. Among these states Kerala has the highest land degradation (6.71%) and Jharkhand has the lowest per cent (4.95%) of land under degradation.

In the third order category of states where the land degradation is medium (2.57-4.57%), Seven states are included, i.e. Madhyapradesh, Karnataka, Chhattisgarh, Andhrapradesh, Goa, Maharashtra and Arunachalpradesh. Among these states Madhyapradesh has the highest land degradation (4.57%) and Arunachalpradesh has the lowest (2.57%) area under land degradation.

In the fourth category, six states are included i.e. Uttarakhand, West Bengal, Orissa, Tamil Nadu, Himachalpradesh and Delhi. In these states land degradation is low (1.89-2.57%). Among these states Uttarakhand has the highest (2.57%) land degradation and Delhi has the lowest (1.89%) area under land degradation.

In the fifth and the last category of states again there are only six states i.e. Gujarat, Bihar, Haryana, Punjab, Jammu & Kashmir, Andaman & Nicobar and Sikkim respectively. In these states land degradation is very low (0.85-1.6%). Among these states Gujarat has the highest (1.6%) land degradation and Sikkim has the lowest (0.85%) area under land degradation.

TABLE- 5 DISTRICT WISE TOTAL GEOGRAPHICAL AREA AND DEGRADED LAND IN BIHAR - 2011

S.No.	DISTRICTS	TGA	LD	% LD OF TGA
1	Araria	284	2	0.70
2	Aurangabad	330	43	13.03
3	Banka	308	72	23.38
4	Begusarai	192	30	15.63
5	Bhabhua	331	114	34.44
6	Bhagalpur	257	73	28.40
7	Bhojpur	246	93	37.80
8	Buxar	163	23	14.11
9	Darbhanga	229	37	16.16
10	Gaya	406	74	18.23
11	Gopalganj	203	77	37.93
12	Jahanabad	157	3	1.91
13	Jamui	311	43	13.83
14	Katihar	306	59	19.28
15	Khagaria	149	24	16.11
16	Kishanganj	188	20	10.64

17	Lukeesarai	123	2	1.63
18	Mdhepura	179	2	1.12
19	Madhubani	351	4	1.14
20	Munger	142	2	1.41
21	Muzaffarpur	350	67	19.14
22	Nalanda	235	22	9.36
23	Nawada	251	21	8.37
24	W Champaran	523	43	8.22
25	Patna	319	83	26.02
26	E Champaran	398	7	1.76
27	Purnia	223	30	13.45
28	Rohtas	382	81	21.20
29	Saharsa	170	5	2.94
30	Samastipur	290	67	23.10
31	Saran	265	50	18.87
32	Sheikhpura	69	0	0.00
33	Seohar	44	0	0.00
34	Sitamarhi	220	0	0.00
35	Siwan	223	3	1.35
36	Supaul	241	6	2.49
37	Vaishali	203	56	27.59
	TOTAL	9261	1338	490.73
	TGA – Total Geographical Area (Hectare), LD – Land degraded (Hectare)			

On the basis of the above table, the following table-6 has been prepared in which land degradation percent of total geographical area, rank and their percentile has been calculated in Bihar according to the available statistics of 2011.

DATA ANALYSIS

So far as the wasteland area statistics of Bihar is concerned, out of 37 districts, land degradation per cent out of total geographical area is zero in three districts i.e. Sheikhpura, Seohar and Sitamarhi districts. These districts stand at 35th rank according to the given table-

6. The rest of the 34 districts on the basis of per cent of land degradation have been categorized into five types, i.e. very high, high, medium, low, and very low.

In the first order category where the land degradation is very high (28.41-37.93%), there are only three districts, i.e. Gopalganj, Bhojpur, and Bhabhua respectively in their descending order of land degradation. Among these districts Gopalganj has the highest land degradation (37.93%), and Bhabhua has the lowest per cent (34.44%) land under degradation.

Similarly, in the second order of the districts in Bihar where the land degradation is high (19.29-28.40%) includes Bhagalpur, Vaishali, Patna, Banka, Samastipur and Rohtas. In this category only six districts are

included and are in their descending order of land degradation. Among these districts, Bhagalpur has the highest land degradation (28.4%) and Rohtas has the lowest percent of land degradation (21.20%).

TABLE – 6 LAND DEGRADATION PERCENT OF TOTAL GEOGRAPHICAL AREA, RANK AND PERCENTILE IN BIHAR - 2011

S.No. OF TABLE-5	LD % OF TGA	RANK	PERCENTILE
11	37.93	1	100.00%
7	37.80	2	97.20%
5	34.44	3	94.40%
6	28.40	4	91.60%
37	27.59	5	88.80%
25	26.02	6	86.10%
3	23.38	7	83.30%
30	23.10	8	80.50%
28	21.20	9	77.70%
14	19.28	10	75.00%
21	19.14	11	72.20%
31	18.87	12	69.40%
10	18.23	13	66.60%
9	16.16	14	63.80%
15	16.11	15	61.10%
4	15.63	16	58.30%
8	14.11	17	55.50%
13	13.83	18	52.70%
27	13.45	19	50.00%
2	13.03	20	47.20%
16	10.64	21	44.40%
22	9.36	22	41.60%
23	8.37	23	38.80%
24	8.22	24	36.10%
29	2.94	25	33.30%

36	2.49	26	30.50%
12	1.91	27	27.70%
26	1.76	28	25.00%
17	1.63	29	22.20%
20	1.41	30	19.40%
35	1.35	31	16.60%
19	1.14	32	13.80%
18	1.12	33	11.10%
1	0.70	34	8.30%
32	0.00	35	0.00%
33	0.00	35	0.00%
34	0.00	35	0.00%
TGA – Total Geographical Area (Hectare), LD – Land degraded (Hectare)			

In the third order category of districts where the land degradation is medium (10.65-19.27%) includes Katihar, Muzaffarpur, Saran, Gaya, Darbhanga, Khagaria, Begusarai, Buxar, Jamui, Purnia, and Aurangabad. In this category eleven districts are included among which Katihar has the highest percent (19.28%) of land degradation and Aurangabad has the lowest per cent (13.03%) of land degradation.

In the fourth order category, only four districts are included, i.e. Kishanganj, Nalanda, Nawada and West Champaran respectively, where the land degradation is low (2.95-10.64%). These districts are also in their descending order of their land degradation. Among these districts, Kishanganj has the

highest per cent (10.64%) of the land under degradation and West Champaran has the lowest per cent (8.22%) of the land degradation.

In the fifth and the last category of districts where the land degradation is very low (0-2.94%) includes Saharsa, Supaul, Jahanabad, East Champaran, Lukeesarai, Munger, Siwan, Madhubani, Madhepura, Araria, Sitamarhi, Seohar, and Sheikhpura districts. These are thirteen in number and are also in their descending order of their land degradation. Among these districts, Saharsa has the highest per cent (2.94%) of land degradation and Araria has the lowest per cent (0.7%) land under degradation, map-2.

MAP - 2

CONCLUSION

The task of providing food security to our country's burgeoning population is becoming increasingly difficult. This challenge must and needs to be met in the face of the changing consumption patterns, impacts of the climate change and degradation of the finite land and water resources. Management of land resources in general, and crop production methods that will keep pace with country's food needs, sustaining environment, blunting impact of climate change, preserving and enhancing natural resources, and supporting livelihood of farmers and rural population in the country. Thus, there is a pressing need for enlarging area under arable lands by the way of reclaiming degraded lands for sustainable intensification of agriculture, in which crop yields can be increased without compromising

and yielding to adverse environmental impacts and without reducing area under forests.

In the population rich countries with finite land resources, agricultural natural resource security is of utmost importance. Further, because the crop yields and productivity of the 'favoured agricultural regions' have plateaued out, it is essential that the degraded and wastelands are rehabilitated and rejuvenated so that such lands are rendered cultivable and may become effective in supporting food crop production, agro-forestry and forestry-based land systems. Further, global environmental change and variability are forcing irreparable damage to the arable lands adjoining degraded lands, water and biodiversity resources. These would have serious consequences on food production and food security in the coming years.

RECOMMENDATIONS

This study on the degraded and wastelands of India in a way contains the first approximation of the harmonized results of the inter-institutional effort. Several points of recommendations for immediate application are indicated. These are detailed as follows:

- Planning for land conservation should be prioritized based on the severity of the degradational problems arising owing to water and wind erosions and anthropogenic activities like agro-forestry, silviculture and social forestry should be adopted to protect agricultural lands from further deterioration arising out of degradational processes. Afforestation of degraded and wastelands should be given priority.
- As conservation and land rehabilitation measures are highly expensive, the area for reclamation should be prioritized based on the severity of the land degradation, the nature of the extent of the problem and the proposed land use. The maps and the data given in this study can be effectively used for such initiatives.
- Reclamation of acidic, saline and sodic soils should get priority in the districts that are severally affected by them in different states. These are chemical land degradational processes and materials needed for their amelioration and reclamation is easily available. The materials should make available in a planned manner in accordance with the severity of the problem prevailing in the districts/states.
- Where complex problems of degradation like water erosion, acidity and water erosion salinity and sodicity co-exist, the research agenda needs to be re-oriented to bring out a list of “good practices” for amelioration of soil health of such degraded lands.
- Cultivation of bio-fuel producing plants and fuel trees/crops should be encouraged in the degraded and wastelands. This is an essential step for environmental protection. The data sets and maps of this study can help the government.

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